

Phone Theft | Emergency Kit

Print a copy of this kit, fill it out, and keep it in a safe place.

Step 0

Better **SAFE** than **SORRY**

Turn on your phone's backup feature or use a third-party app to save your photos to the cloud. That way, you can **wipe your stolen phone remotely** without losing anything important.

Please **DO NOT PANIC**. We will **guide** you **through** the **most essential steps**.

Step 1

LOCK & TRACK your **PHONE**.

Do you know your **Apple/Google** username and password? **Can you sign in** on a **different device without** your phone? Do you have a **2nd device** listed as **"trusted"** in your account settings?

Once you **mark** your phone **as lost**, **Apple/Google Pay** is **suspended** and you can **add contact information**, which is **shown on the lock screen**.

Your
Apple / Google
Account

Your
2nd Trusted
Device

Be careful, **never put yourself in danger** while tracking; instead, **ask the police for help!**

Step 2

FREEZE your **SIM CARD**.

Freeze your SIM card to **prevent identity theft** or the **leakage** of **two-factor SMS** codes.

Fill in the helpline number **of your wireless carrier** that you need to call to freeze your SIM card.

Your
Phone
Number

24/7
Emergency
Helpline

Phones from 2019 or newer can be **tracked offline**, so freezing your SIM will not affect tracking.

Step 3

MONITOR or **FREEZE** your **BANK CARDS**.

If you have any payment information or cards stored on your device, please monitor it closely.

Fill in the helpline number **of your bank** that you need to call to freeze your cards.

Your
Bank Name /
Acc. Number

24/7
Emergency
Helpline

This **might stop** all ongoing **legitimate transactions** too. Reordering may come with a **service fee**.

Step 4

FILE a **REPORT WITH** the **POLICE**.

The officer will ask for your device's **IMEI** to blacklist it, making it more difficult to resell the phone. You can find the IMEI by **dialing *#06#** or on your **purchase receipt**.

Please fill in your device's **brand, model**, and **IMEI number(s)**.

Your
Device
Brand / Model

Your
IMEI
Number(s)

Filing the theft with the police will help you in case of any **subsequent identity theft attempts** or other **financial fraud** and can be important for **insurance reasons**.

Monitor your online **accounts**, **change** your most important **passwords** (banking and email), watch out for suspicious activity and unsolicited online transactions like purchases and subscriptions you did not initiate. Be **extra careful** with messages **asking for your password** or to **remove the stolen phone** from your Apple / Google account, these are **scams**.